

**COMPRESSION BUCKLING OF ANISOTROPIC FIBRE-REINFORCED
FLAT RECTANGULAR PLATES WITH CENTRAL CIRCULAR CUT-OUTS**

G.J. Turvey and K. Sadeghipour
Department of Engineering,
University of Lancaster,
Lancaster, Lancashire, LA1 4YR,
U.K.

ABSTRACT

A finite element program which incorporates triangular elements with five degrees of freedom per node has been developed for the initial buckling analysis of rectangular, symmetrically laminated plates with arbitrary cut-outs. The accuracy of the program is established via a series of comparisons with alternative theoretical and experimental data for unperforated anisotropic plates and specially orthotropic plates with circular cut-outs. New compression buckling data are presented for anisotropic GFRP and CFRP square plates with and without central circular cut-outs. The data indicate that changes in the degree of anisotropy produce smaller changes in the buckling coefficient than result from changing the flexural support conditions from simply supported to clamped.

NOTATION

a : Plate length
b : Plate width
d : Hole diameter
 E_L, E_T : Longitudinal and transverse lamina elastic moduli
 G_{LT} : In-plane lamina shear modulus
h : Plate thickness
K : Dimensionless initial buckling coefficient for compression
 N_x : Edge stress resultant in the x-direction
P : Total uniaxial edge buckling load
 ϕ : Fibre-orientation angle
 λ : Eigenvalue
 σ : Uniaxial compression buckling stress

Subscripts/Superscripts

cr : Value of variable at buckling
o : Value of variable for unperforated plate
* : Value of variable associated with $\phi \neq 0^\circ$
" : Value of variable for $\phi = 0^\circ$

INTRODUCTION

Flat rectangular plates with holes or cut-outs occur quite often in thin-walled structures. A major factor influencing the design of these structures is the buckling resistance of their component plates. The development of initial buckling data for the design of plates with cut-outs is, therefore, of practical importance. Indeed, this fact has long been recognised. About forty years ago Levy et al. [1] published the first significant buckling analysis of a plate with a cut-out. They considered the case of a uniaxially compressed square, isotropic, simply supported plate with a central circular hole. Other important early analyses of this basic problem [2-4] accounted for clamped boundaries and distinguished between uniform edge stress and strain induced buckling. The Rayleigh-Ritz energy method was used for all of these analyses.

In the late 1960s the advent of modern high speed digital computers enabled the limitations of the Rayleigh-Ritz method of analysis, viz. the construction of suitable functions to satisfy practical kinematic boundary conditions, to be circumscribed. Thus, a combination of the Rayleigh-Ritz and finite element methods was used to generate new buckling data for plates with cut-outs [5 & 6]. Finite element analyses were used to determine the pre-buckling stress distributions within the plate - this being the major difficulty with the pure Rayleigh-Ritz method.

More recently, the need to provide comprehensive data on the buckling of isotropic plates with cut-outs has been fully recognised and, because of its flexibility, the finite method of analysis has been used almost exclusively to meet this need. Thus, data are now available for a range of: cut-out shapes, sizes and locations, plate edge conditions and de-stabilising edge stresses/strains [7-13]. This wealth of design data is being added to continually and enables the instability design of thin-walled isotropic structures with cut-outs to proceed with reasonable confidence.

Nowadays, by no means all thin-walled structures are fabricated from isotropic materials. Indeed, many structures of this type are made of advanced composite materials, e.g. glass and carbon fibre-reinforced plastics (GFRP and CFRP). Like their isotropic (usually metal) counterparts, these GFRP and CFRP thin-walled structures often incorporate cut-outs. Moreover, these new structural materials are inherently orthotropic, i.e. the stiffness in the fibre-direction is significantly greater than that transverse to it. There is, therefore, an obvious need to develop initial buckling data for the design of orthotropic and anisotropic rectangular plates with cut-outs. This requirement is gradually beginning to be recognised and some design data has been published recently. In particular, Marshall and his associates [14-17] have used the semi-energy method to generate uniaxial compression buckling data for specially orthotropic plates with circular cut-outs. Nemeth [18 & 19] too has considered the same problem. He reduced the problem to an equivalent one-dimensional form and obtained solutions using a combined series - finite-difference method. The analyses reported in [14-19] are highly complex and suffer from the same drawbacks as in [1-4], viz. that only a very limited range of in-plane edge conditions may be accommodated. Moreover, only orthotropy and not anisotropy may be properly accounted for in these analyses. This constitutes a further shortcoming, since many symmetric lamination schemes of practical importance lead to anisotropic plate stiffnesses. Larsson [20] has recently used the finite element method to analyse the compression buckling of rectangular orthotropic plates with central circular cut-outs, but he only presented data applicable to plates with small holes (maximum hole-size ratio of 0.3).

The objective of this paper is to present some results from a special purpose finite element computer program NEWPLATE which has been developed for the initial buckling analysis of symmetrically laminated anisotropic plates with cut-outs. The accuracy/validity of the program has been established via a series of buckling results comparisons with other analytical and experimental data for unperforated anisotropic and perforated orthotropic square plates in compression. Space restrictions prevent a full presentation of these results comparisons. New results are presented for the uniaxial compression buckling of anisotropic square plates with/without central circular cut-outs. The effects of varying: the hole-size ratio, the flexural edge conditions and the degree of anisotropy on the initial buckling coefficient ratio are all illustrated. It is concluded that for a given hole-size ratio the effect of changing the flexural edge conditions from simply supported to clamped produces a greater change in the initial buckling coefficient ratio than do changes in the degree of anisotropy.

PLATE GEOMETRY, MATERIAL PROPERTIES, LOAD AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Details of the plate geometry and the positive co-ordinate system are shown in Fig. 1. As only central circular cut-outs are considered here, the plate geometry may be defined in terms of just two parameters, viz. the aspect ratio, b/a , and the hole-size ratio, d/a . Buckling analyses have been undertaken for square plates, i.e. $b/a = 1$, and for hole-size ratios in the range: 0 - 0.7.

Figure 1. Rectangular flat plate with a cut-out: geometry and positive co-ordinate system.

GFRP and CFRP are generally regarded as the most widely used fibre-reinforced composite materials and, therefore, buckling analyses have been undertaken for each of them. Representative values have been assumed for their elastic constants and they are listed in Table 1.

By varying the fibre-direction angle, ϕ , with respect to the plate axes (see Fig. 1), both the extensional and flexural plate stiffnesses may be varied. For the analyses described here, the angle, ϕ , was varied between 0° and 90° and the plate was assumed to consist of a single layer or lamina, i.e. the plate stiffnesses correspond to those of a homogenous anisotropic plate.

TABLE 1
Elastic constants for typical GFRP and CFRP materials

Material	E_L (N/mm ²)	E_T (N/mm ²)	G_{LT} (N/mm ²)	ν_{LT}
GFRP	10400	3100	2142	0.3
CFRP	130000	9000	4800	0.28

The pre-buckling stress field within the plate plays an important role in determining its initial buckling stress. This stress field depends not only on the size, shape and location of the cut-out, but also on the nature of the de-stabilising load. The two types of uniaxial compression considered here are: uniform uniaxial edge stress and uniform uniaxial edge strain.

The initial buckling stress is also very dependent on the plate edge conditions. Two types of flexural condition are assumed active, i.e. all four plate edges are either simply supported or clamped. For uniaxial compression induced buckling the transverse in-plane restraint enforced along the unloaded plate edges also affects the pre-buckling stress field. Again, two cases are distinguished: zero and full restraint.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The finite element computer program NEWPLATE, which has been specially developed for the analysis of plates with cut-outs, has a modular format and may be run in either interactive or batch mode. Triangular elements with five degrees of freedom per node, i.e. u , v , w , w' and w'' , are used in the current version of the program. The element in-plane displacement components, u and v , are represented by complete linear polynomials and the out-of-plane displacement, w , by a truncated cubic polynomial.

A feature of the program is a semi-automatic facility to constrain the unloaded/loaded edges of the plate to remain straight, so that, for example, buckling under controlled edge strain may be simulated. Such displacement control is accomplished by effectively adding spring stiffnesses to the edge nodes of the plate.

PROGRAM VERIFICATION ANALYSES

A large number of check analyses were made in order to establish the accuracy of the buckling stresses computed with the program NEWPLATE. Initially, isotropic rectangular plates without cut-outs were analysed to determine the influence of the de-stabilising stress distribution (compression or shear) and the flexural edge conditions (simply supported or clamped) on the solution convergence as the finite element mesh was progressively refined. A smaller number of similar studies were also undertaken for specially orthotropic rectangular plates. These studies showed that quite coarse meshes, equivalent to 10 x 10 over the whole plate, gave results which were typically within 2% of the exact value of the initial buckling coefficient.

The modelling of circular cut-outs and anisotropy were verified by comparing buckling coefficients, derived from a variety of sources, for anisotropic

plates and specially orthotropic plates with cut-outs with corresponding values obtained from the program NEWPLATE. Some comments on these results comparisons are given below.

The initial buckling coefficient data for simply supported, square anisotropic plates in uniform, uniaxial compression reported in [21] were used to compare with the NEWPLATE buckling results and verify that material anisotropy had been correctly incorporated into the program. The results comparison was found to be very satisfactory.

In order to verify the modelling of circular cut-outs, the NEWPLATE finite element results for compression buckling of simply supported, square GFRP plates were compared with Marshall et al.'s theoretical and experimental data [14 & 15]. Space limitations preclude the presentation of any details of the results comparison, which was satisfactory, but the finite element results are listed in Table 2. They demonstrate clearly that constraining the transverse displacement along the unloaded edge reduces the initial buckling load and that strain controlled buckling loads are greater than stress controlled buckling loads.

TABLE 2
Buckling load ratios for perforated square GFRP orthotropic plates
in uniaxial compression

Hole-Size Ratio (d/a)	Uniform Stress, In-Plane Free	Uniform Stress, In-Plane Fixed	Uniform Strain, In-Plane Fixed
0.0	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000
0.1	0.95624	0.94705	0.94920
0.2	0.90653	0.86570	0.87490
0.3	0.87500	0.79090	0.81290
0.4	0.86329	0.73080	0.77290
0.5	0.90540	0.69830	0.78490
0.6	0.97218	0.67960	0.83300
0.7	1.08858	0.66420	0.94570

BUCKLING RESULTS FOR ANISOTROPIC PLATES WITH CUT-OUTS

There appears to be a complete lack of data on the buckling of rectangular anisotropic plates with cut-outs, although, as mentioned above, some data exist for orthotropic plates (the degenerate situation with respect to the material properties). Thus, the program NEWPLATE has been used to generate buckling data for anisotropic material plates. The data correspond to the GFRP and CFRP materials whose properties are given in Table 1.

The first set of anisotropic plate buckling results obtained were for square plates without cut-outs (a zero hole-size ratio). The plates were assumed to be either simply supported or clamped along all edges. Buckling was induced by means of a uniform, uniaxial edge stress and the transverse in-plane displacement was unrestrained along the unloaded edges. Of particular interest are the buckling modes in the compression direction (the mode in the transverse direction was, in all cases, a single half-wave). The simply supported GFRP plates buckled in a single half-wave irrespective of the fibre-orientation angle, ϕ , whereas for clamped GFRP plates the mode changed from three to two half-waves when $\phi > 50^\circ$. The buckling modes for clamped

CFRP plates are similar to those for GFRP plates. However, for simply supported CFRP plates the mode changes from one to two half-waves when $\phi > 50^\circ$.

Buckling stress ratios versus fibre-orientation angle are shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) for GFRP and CFRP plates respectively. For GFRP plates the buckling stress ratio decreases almost linearly with increasing ϕ for both simply supported and clamped conditions. Moreover, the buckling stress ratio falls more rapidly for both GFRP and CFRP plates when the edges are clamped. In both cases the maximum reduction in the buckling stress ratio corresponds to $\phi = 90^\circ$, i.e. with the fibres perpendicular to the compression direction. For GFRP plates the maximum reductions in the buckling stress ratio amount to 6% and 27% under simply supported and clamped edge conditions respectively. The corresponding reductions for CFRP plates (see Fig. 2(b)) are 45% and 62% under simply supported and clamped edge conditions respectively. Furthermore, for simply supported CFRP plates there is little change in the buckling stress ratio for ϕ -values in the range: $0^\circ - 45^\circ$ and for clamped CFRP plates for ϕ -values in the range: $60^\circ - 90^\circ$.

Figure 2. Critical buckling stress ratio versus fibre-orientation angle for square anisotropic plates in uniaxial compression (uniform stress, in-plane free case): (a) GFRP plates and (b) CFRP plates.

The second set of anisotropic plate finite element computations were intended to quantify the effect of the hole-size ratio on the buckling response. The anisotropy of each plate was fixed at its maximum value by setting the angle, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and the hole-size ratio was varied from 0 to 0.5. Buckling

TABLE 3

Critical buckling coefficients and stress ratios for square anisotropic ($\phi = 45^\circ$) GFRP plates in compression (uniform stress, in-plane free case)

Hole Diameter Panel Width	Simply Supported Edges		Clamped Edges	
	$\frac{N_x a^2}{E_L h^3}$	Kcr/Ko	$\frac{N_x a^2}{E_L h^3}$	Kcr/Ko
0.0	1.897	1.00	4.500	1.00
0.1	1.858	0.98	4.315	0.96
0.2	1.775	0.94	4.280	0.95
0.3	1.753	0.92	4.317	0.96
0.4	1.765	0.93	4.790	1.07
0.5	1.886	0.99	5.596	1.24

Figure 3. Uniaxial buckling of simply supported and clamped square GFRP plates (uniform stress, in-plane free case): (a) Buckling coefficient ratio versus hole-size ratio; and (b) Critical buckling coefficient versus hole-size ratio.

was again induced by a uniform, uniaxial edge stress and the unloaded edges were unrestrained against in-plane movement. The resulting buckling stresses etc. for both simply supported and clamped edge conditions are listed in Table 3. This tabulated data is, for convenience, also plotted in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). Clearly, the buckling coefficients of clamped plates are more sensitive to the size of the cut-out. Moreover, when the cut-out is large the buckling stress may even exceed that for the corresponding unperforated plate.

The final set of results presented illustrate the influence of anisotropy on the buckling response of GFRP square plates. The hole-size ratio was fixed at 0.3 and the fibre-direction angle, ϕ , was varied between 0° and 90° . All other conditions were as for the second set of computations. The predicted buckling coefficients etc. are given in Table 4 and the buckling stress ratios are shown as functions of ϕ in Fig. 4. It may be observed that for simply supported plates this ratio decreases linearly by about 3% as ϕ increases from 0° to 90° . Similar behaviour was observed for unperforated simply supported anisotropic plates (see Fig. 2(a)). For clamped GFRP plates, however, there is a much greater drop (about 18%) in the buckling stress ratio over the same ϕ -range; and the greater part occurs between $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 40^\circ$, which contrasts sharply with the unperforated case (see Fig. 2(a)).

TABLE 4

Critical buckling stress ratios for square anisotropic GFRP plates with a hole-size ratio of 0.3 (uniform stress, in-plane free case)

Fibre Orientation (ϕ°)	Clamped σ^*/σ''	Simply Supported σ^*/σ''
0	1.000	1.000
10	0.982	0.999
20	0.939	0.998
30	0.889	0.996
40	0.830	0.992
50	0.830	0.987
60	0.823	0.980
70	0.820	0.975
80	0.816	0.972
90	0.815	0.971

CONCLUSIONS

A special purpose triangular finite element program NEWPLATE for the initial buckling analysis of symmetrically laminated anisotropic rectangular plates with arbitrary shaped cut-outs has been developed and described in outline. The programme has been verified by a series of comparisons with alternative theoretical and experimental buckling results for orthotropic plates with circular cut-outs and for unperforated anisotropic plates. In general, the finite element analysis was able to provide initial buckling stress predictions accurate to within a few percent without undue mesh refinement. Some new results have been presented for the compression buckling of square anisotropic GFRP plates with central circular cut-outs. These results show, in general,

that material anisotropy produces smaller variations in the plate buckling stress than those caused by changing the plate edge conditions from simply supported to clamped.

Figure 4. Critical stress ratio versus fibre-orientation angle for square anisotropic plates in compression (uniform stress, in-plane free case and hole-size ratio of 0.3).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described in this paper was undertaken as part of a research project supported by a grant from the University Research Committee. The authors wish to record their appreciation to the committee for their support, and also to the Department of Engineering for providing computing facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Levy, S., Woolley, R.M. and Kroll, W.D., Instability of a simply supported square plate with a reinforced circular hole in edge compression, J. Res. Nat. Bur. Standards, 1947, 39, 571-7.
2. Kumai, T., Elastic stability of the square plate with a circular central hole under edge thrust, Proc. 1st Japan. Nat. Cong. App. Mech., 1951, 81-6.
3. Schlack, A.L., Elastic stability of pierced square plates, Exp. Mech., 1964, 4, 167-72.
4. Yoshiki, M., Fujita, Y., Kawamura, A. and Arai, H., Instability of plates with holes (first report), Proc. Soc. Naval Arch. Japan, 1967, 137-45.
5. Kawai, T. and Ohtsubo, H., A method of solution for the complicated buckling problems of elastic plates with combined use of Rayleigh-Ritz's procedure in the finite element method, Proc. 2nd Conf. Matrix Meth. Struct. Mech., AFFDL-TR-68-150, 1968, 967-94.
6. Ritchie, D. and Rhodes, J., Buckling and post-buckling behaviour of plates with holes, Aero. Quart., 1975, XXIV, 281-96.

7. Shanmugan, N. and Narayanan, R., Elastic buckling of perforated square plates for various loading and edge conditions, Proc. Int. Conf. Finite Element Meth., Beijing, China, 1982, 241-45.
8. Sabir, A.B. and Chow, F.Y., Elastic buckling of flat panels containing circular and square holes, Proc. Conf. Instabil. and Plastic Collapse of Steel Structures, Manchester, 1983, 311-21.
9. Azizian, Z.G. and Roberts, T.M., Instability and strength of perforated plates, Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng. (Pt. 2: Res. & Theory), 1983, 75, 761.
10. Narayanan, R. and Der Avanessian, N.G.V., Elastic buckling of perforated plates under shear, Thin-Walled Struct., 1984, 2, 51-74.
11. Sabir, A.B. and Chow, F.Y., Elastic buckling of plates containing eccentrically located circular holes, Thin-Walled Struct., 1986, 4, 135-50.
12. Yettram, A.L. and Brown, C.J., The elastic stability of square perforated plates, Computers & Structures, 1985, 21, 1267-72.
13. Yettram, A.L. and Brown, C.J., The elastic stability of square perforated plates under bi-axial loading, Computers & Structures, 1986, 22, 589-94.
14. Marshall, I.H., Little, W. and El Tayeby, M.M., The stability of composite panels with holes, Proc. Reinforced Plast. Cong., Brighton, 1984, 139-42.
15. Marshall, I.H., Little, W., El Tayeby, M.M. and Williams, J., Buckling of perforated composite plates - an approximate solution, Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., 1986, C30, 29-33.
16. Marshall, I.H. and Paul, J.S., The stability characteristics of thin composite plates with multiple access holes, Proc. 4th Cong. de Plast., Brazil, 1986.
17. Marshall, I.H., Little, W. and El Tayeby, M.M., Composite panels with circular cut-outs: some design guidelines, Proc. Reinforced Plast. Cong., Nottingham, 1986, 91-4.
18. Nemeth, M.P., A buckling analysis for rectangular orthotropic plates with centrally located cut-outs, NASA TM 86263, December 1984.
19. Nemeth, M.P., Stein, M. and Johnson, E.R., An approximate buckling analysis for rectangular orthotropic plates with centrally located cutouts, NASA TP 2528, February 1986.
20. Larsson, P-L, On the buckling of orthotropic compressed plates with circular holes, J. Comp. Struct., 1987, 7, (In Press).
21. Ashton, J.E. and Whitney, J.M., Theory of Laminated Plates, Technomic, Stamford, Connecticut, 1970.